

PREPARING FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS FOR DIGITAL EDUCATION ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: The article discusses pedagogical technologies used in the digital educational environment. Particular attention is paid to preparing future technology teachers to use distance learning and blended learning technologies. The experience of preparing future technology teachers for organizing training in the digital educational environment of a school is presented using the example of the subject “Methodology of Technological Education”, implemented at the Tashkent State Economic University named after Nizomiya.

Keywords: digital educational environment, modern pedagogical technologies, distance education, mixed education.

INTRODUCTION

The digital age demands a reconsideration of traditional teaching and learning methods. Rapid technological advancements in education lead to a paradigm shift from traditional teaching to the use of modern pedagogical technologies. Modern digital technologies offer numerous new educational opportunities and approaches that make education more effective, enriching, and facilitate the personalization of learning processes, while supporting students.

An analysis of publications on the digitalization of education [3, 9, 10] indicates that authors have identified digital-communication technologies for universal use; pedagogical technologies based on the use of digital tools; and digital technologies that ensure the development of necessary knowledge, skills, and professional competencies among students. We believe that the list of teaching technologies in a digital education environment should now be supplemented with the latest technologies developed in accordance with various regulatory documents. These include internet technologies, virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence, robotics, and big data.

Among pedagogical technologies, researchers highlight digital pedagogical technologies (such as project methods, applied research technologies, etc.) which can include the use of ICT as auxiliary pedagogical tools and digital pedagogical technologies (such as flipped learning, mobile technologies, distance education, and others).

Preparing future technology teachers to use these technologies within the digital education environment of schools is a crucial task for teacher education. Additionally, students must master the necessary digital educational resources, including those located on local educational platforms; learn to select the appropriate digital tools for various pedagogical technologies; acquire modern digital assessment tools; be prepared to organize the educational process in a distance format; and possess skills to organize extracurricular projects and educational research activities within the digital education environment. Moreover, solving this problem

must be implemented within the appropriate digital education environment of the university.

Literature Analysis

Research on enhancing the preparation of technology teachers, developing them within the digital education environment, and the role of ICT in improving the quality of education has been conducted by numerous domestic scholars, including U.N. Nishonaliyev, A.R. Khodjabayev, N.Sh. Shodiyev, N.A. Muslimov, Kh.I. Ibragimov, E.I. Ro'ziev, O'.Q. Tolipov, N. Saidahmedov, D. Ergashev, Sh.S. Sharipov, O. Abduquddusov, E.T. Choriev, O. To'raqulov, J. Hamidov, A. Jo'raev, U. Jumanazarov, O. Qo'ysinov, and F.S. Turabekov, among others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of the article begins with an analysis of scientific and increasingly popular sources, analyzing the professional activities and technological capacity of technology teachers, and the importance and role of their professional competencies in enhancing the quality of technology classes. Methods for analyzing the composition of computer technologies in improving the quality of classes, working programs and manuals for enhancing education quality, scientific generalizations on the use of modern web tools, and interview methods with prospective technology teachers were also employed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the national development goals for the country up to the year 2030 is the digital transformation of the most crucial sectors of the economy and the social sector. A significant emphasis is placed on transforming education within the formation of the digital economy. The trends in digital transformation of the general education system have become virtually undisputed [1].

In our country, the task of updating digital-communication infrastructure, teaching, and creating a digital education system that fosters self-development and self-education values among students of all types and levels of educational institutions is of great importance. In this regard, pedagogical education faces the tasks of enhancing the skills of future technology teachers to work in a digital education environment; incorporating digital content and ecological solutions used in modern digital schools into educational programs; and forming ICT competencies among prospective pedagogical education undergraduates.

Special attention should be given to the integration of future technology teachers with digital technologies and familiarizing them with pedagogically appropriate modern pedagogical technologies. This issue can be resolved within the methodological disciplines or specifically within the scope of a "Digital Technologies" course.

Within the context of a science-based digital education environment, implementing a system-activity approach in education using the "1 student: 1 computer" technology is considered effective. "1 student: 1 computer" implies that the computer is the primary tool for teaching, employing methods such as network interaction, information acquisition, and the creation of digital objects and services [12, 13].

The "1 student: 1 computer" education model creates real conditions to enhance motivation and stimulate cognitive activity among students. These conditions may include collaborative production activities, the use of internet resources, creating socially significant products, mass presentations, self and peer assessment, among others.

In utilizing this model, the components of a science-based digital education environment may include: the content on the school's local network, digital educational resources, the teacher's website, Google Classroom service, digital tools for organizing collaborative activities, digital

tools for creative and project activities, and tools for organizing assessment and reflection.

In mastering digital pedagogical technologies, prospective pedagogical education undergraduates present digital tools for implementation with the help of various visualization tools (mind maps, infographics, SWOT analysis, etc.), discussing their advantages and the difficulties encountered in use.

One of the most pressing and politically relevant issues in education today is distance learning. During the quarantine measures implemented in response to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, when a mandatory shift to distance learning was enforced globally, the challenges of organizing distance education became apparent. Every educational institution and every teacher has the task to swiftly adapt to distance teaching formats and possibilities. Not all teachers were prepared to solve this problem. Therefore, the need for future technology teachers to master distance teaching formats is undoubtedly crucial.

Students master various methods of delivering content using distance teaching technologies to facilitate synchronous and asynchronous communication [4]. Future teachers undertake tasks such as using Moodle elements; designing the use of local digital platforms, cloud storage, and Web 2.0 services; creating interactive worksheets and assessment materials for organizing individual and collaborative student activities; and developing skills in selecting, analyzing, and evaluating digital resources.

Despite the increasing prevalence of distance technologies, they are not always sufficiently effective: students may lack the motivation and self-organization skills necessary to adequately complete and succeed in the course. Therefore, the most promising form of organizing the educational process in a digital learning environment includes blended learning, which combines online and face-to-face education formats.

As for the instrumental support for implementing blended learning, it could involve digital educational resources; electronic textbooks; materials placed on local digital platforms; learning management systems; cloud technologies; Web 2.0 services; and other digital tools [2].

Examples of organizing the educational process using electronic textbooks are provided in the methodological guide [7], which also includes various models of blended learning and pedagogical scenarios for lessons in various subjects using different digital tools [11]. Consequently, future technology teachers design similar lessons in their respective subjects.

Currently, many modern digital technologies have didactic potential, and therefore they can be utilized in the educational process to enhance its pedagogical effectiveness and socio-economic efficiency.

Today, it is essential to emphasize the need for schools to utilize technologies such as blockchain, big data technologies, artificial intelligence, virtual and augmented reality, and robotics in the educational process. To master these technologies, pedagogical technoparks and quantoriums are being established at our country's pedagogical universities.

At the technopark site, areas related to robotic systems, competitive robotics, virtual and augmented reality, artificial intelligence, computer graphics, and computer-aided design are developed. Regarding digital educational technologies, the use of digital tools and services makes their application more effective. Future teachers gain confidence in this through organizing project activities within the school's digital education environment. Today, digital-communication technologies and, primarily, network technologies provide the instrumental basis for project activities. The development of the internet has created conditions for transferring project activities online.

Monographs [5, 6] and a guide [8] detail the didactic possibilities of various digital tools in

organizing network project activities and the unique characteristics of preparing future teachers to organize project activities for school students. Students analyze various academic and extracurricular projects developed by university teachers and students, and future students develop their scientific projects.

During the course of "Digital Technologies," future teachers are convinced that they can improve the quality of the educational process through digitally well-thought-out organization, discipline, project, and similar aspects of the digital education environment.

CONCLUSIONS

In the context of digital transformation in education, the role of preparing future technology teachers to organize school education within a digital education environment is significantly increasing. Creating conditions for students to master the integration of modern pedagogical and digital technologies into the learning process is one of the main tasks of the "Digital Technologies" course.

During the course, future teachers will acquire the necessary skills to participate in solving the problems of digital transformation of schools and prepare for creating a future science-based digital education environment. Meanwhile, the teachers managing this course must themselves demonstrate skilled use of modern pedagogical technologies in the digital education environment and showcase their abilities to utilize digital resources and services necessary for shaping students' universal and professional competencies.

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